

An *in silico* medicine info kit for effective stakeholder engagement

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INTRODUCTION: *In silico* medicine includes all the practices of computer modelling & simulations (CM&S) for prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of a disease, as well as the development and de-risking of biomedical products. Bringing together all the relevant stakeholders of *in silico* medicine, be it policymakers, clinicians, patients, etc. requires a community effort. As the International Society for *in silico* medicine, we have developed a variety of stakeholder engagement tools to rally the community, through an ***In Silico Medicine Info Kit specifically designed for the modelling community to engage with key stakeholders in the realm of in silico medicine.***

MATERIALS & METHODS: The **strategies for stakeholder engagement** have been developed through direct experience gained from our involvement in EU-funded projects, focused on *in silico* medicine. Here, we briefly outline some of the key strategies and accompanying tools that we developed:

- Guidelines on '**How-to**' conduct '**Delphi study**' and '**surveys**', in the context of *in silico medicine*, for instance to capture the needs and barriers, or awareness and perceptions.
- A step-by-step handbook to organize **focus groups**, featuring pre-designed templates tailored for the field of *in silico* medicine.
- **Focus cards** containing fictive scenarios crafted by *in silico* experts, to foster dynamic discussions and engagement.

Collectively, they provide guidelines, tools and resources, including multimedia examples, for effective stakeholder interaction.

OUTLOOK: *In silico* medicine represents the future of healthcare and has entered into a transformational phase of becoming part of real-life applications. Within this landscape, active engagement with diverse stakeholders such as patients, clinicians, policymakers, and industry leaders is imperative. The "***In silico medicine infokit***" would foster such endeavours, by addressing the unique challenges and needs of *in silico* medicine. We welcome the community to take advantage of the tools, as well as join us to co-create further.

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